

Sherds catalogue: The MaltaPot project

Catalogue of Għar Dalam and Skorba phase pottery sherds selected for archaeometric analysis.

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This catalogue was compiled in 2023. Data collection was carried out between 2018-2020 and 2023. The current or additional data on the sherds can be accessed by emailing Dr Ing J.C. Betts at john.betts@um.edu.mt

Author statement

This catalogue was compiled and written by E. Richard-Trémeau. Dr C Brogan carried out the phase identification and the selection of sherds to be analysed. The data about the sherds were collected by the principal researcher for the MaltaPot project, Dr C. Brogan, and completed later by E. Richard Trémeau (surface treatment, archaeological context, cross-referencing with FRAGSUS and any missing information) and Dr Ing. J.C. Betts. The photographs and micro-photographs were taken by Dr C. Brogan and edited by E. Richard-Trémeau.

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1 Introduction

This catalogue was compiled as part of the MaltaPot project (University of Malta, 2023). This project aims at better understanding the nature of the materials used in Neolithic Malta, mainly dating to the Għar Dalam, Skorba, and Żebbuġ periods. A recent chronology of these periods was published in Hunt et al. (2020). The project used multiple techniques to characterise the pottery sherds: microscopy, polarised light microscope, XRF, XRD and SEM-EDS. Although the results await publication, this catalogue presents the sherds which were analysed using these destructive techniques to provide comparative material whilst safeguarding information about the characteristics of these sherds which have been partially destroyed. This catalogue presents the Għar Dalam and Skorba sherds analysed in the project.

2 Naming convention

The names *Għar Dalam* and *Skorba* are used in Maltese archaeology to designate:

- Archaeological sites,
- Chronological periods,
- Pottery phases, which were named after the site where they were first discovered,

3 Methodology and standards used

Note: when the samples were chosen and studied (2018-2020), the contexts, radio-carbon dates and stratigraphy of the FRAGSUS sites had yet to be fully established (Malone et al., 2020a), and sherds were sampled based on their features (decoration, shape). The MaltaPot samples were selected after the macroscopic and microscopic examination of 162 sherds.

This catalogue was made using an open access Latex script (Richard-Trémeau, 2023).

3.1 Figures

Macroscopic photographs were taken with a copy-stand, using a black background with a dimension and colour scale. The photographs were then modified digitally: the white balance was adjusted, and the interior and exterior surface photographs were assembled on one image over a digitally created black background.

Micro-photographs were taken with a camera (Microtec IS 1000) attached to a binocular stereomicroscope (MEIJI Techno RZ). The micro-photographs width is 15.8mm for all photographs.

3.2 Descriptions

The sherds were described using the typology created by Evans (1971, Figs.30-33), which was recently made more accessible in Malone et al. (2020b, pp.750–1). Sagona (2015, pp.27, 36) was additionally used when necessary.

The macroscopic ware attribution follows established categories in the literature (Evans, 1971; Malone et al., 2020; Sagona, 2015; Trump, 2015). A review of these ware categories is awaiting publication. Detailed fabric descriptions will be published in another paper.

As far as possible, the surface appearance and treatments were described using the vocabulary in Evans (1971) and Malone et al. (2020). The colours are given as Munsell Colour Chart values.

3.3 Chronology

The latest chronology was proposed by McLaughlin et al. (2020c, p.38), and part of the chronology is reproduced in Table 1. The dates for the Early Neolithic are still debated as layers are rarely undisturbed by Late Neolithic activities.

Period	Phase	Dates
Early Neolithic	Għar Dalam	6000-5400 BCE
	Skorba	5400-4800 BCE
Possible hiatus		
Late Neolithic / Temple Period	Żebbuġ	3800-3600 BCE
	Mġarr	3600-3400 BCE
	Ggantija	3400-3100 BCE
	Saflieni	3100-2800 BCE
	Tarxien	2800-2400 BCE

Table 1: Latest chronology for the Maltese Neolithic, after McLaughlin et al. (2020c, p.38)

4 Għar Dalam phase pottery

The eighteen Għar Dalam phase sherds presented here were excavated from the Santa Verna (Gozo) and Skorba (Malta) archaeological sites. The sherds were extracted either from the contexts of the recent FRAGSUS excavations (Brogan et al., 2020; McLaughlin et al., 2020b) or the material excavated by D. Trump in the 60s at Skorba (Trump, 1966; 2015), stored at the National Museum of Archaeology (NMA), Malta. The sites are summarised in the open-access chapters Brogan et al. (2020) and McLaughlin et al. (2020b).

The entries for samples G1005 and G2004 are available in Richard-Trémeau et al. (2023).

G1002

Figure 2: (a) Exterior and interior of G1002 (b) Microphotograph: G1002 ground edge

Other identifiers and previous publications : GD1-4F-23-1 (MaltaPot); SKB23-3 (Malone et al., 2020, 327 and drawing in Fig. 10.8:31) and SKB23_3 (Malone et al., 2020b, p.734).

Description

Sherd type	Body sherd
Typology	Evans Għar Dalam type 3 or 4
Macroscopic Ware classification	Fine ware
Wall thickness	7.26 mm
Surface treatment	Decorated with chevron patterns on exterior surface; smoothed interior surface
Surfaces Interior	10YR 7/3 Very pale brown
Surfaces Exterior	10YR 5/1-5/3 gray to brown
Core colour	7.5YR 6/4 light brown
Margins colour	7.5YR 6/1 gray; 7.5YR 6/4 light brown

Table 2: Characteristics of G1002

Archaeological context This sherd was excavated from a sondage at the site of Skorba in 2015 by the FRAGSUS project (Brogan et al., 2020), stratigraphic unit (23). Għar Dalam phases sherds are residual in this context as this layer was hypothesised to be dated to the Mġarr period. This context is illustrated in section and Harris matrix in Brogan et al. (2020, pp.233–234).

This sherd was sampled because of its diagnostic decoration. This sherd fits the description of fine ware by Evans (1971, p.208).

G1004

Figure 3: (a) Exterior and interior of G1004 (b) Microphotograph: G1004 ground edge

Other identifiers and previous publications : GD1-3F-63-1 (MaltaPot)

Description

Sherd type	Body sherd
Macroscopic Ware classification	Fine ware
Wall thickness	6.65 mm
Surface treatment	Incised/impressed criss-cross pattern with white paste filling on exterior surface
Surfaces Interior	2.5Y 6/4 light reddish brown
Surfaces Exterior	2.5Y 6/3 light reddish brown
Core colour	10YR 7/2 light grey
Margin colour	10YR 7/2 light grey and 6/4 light yellowish brown

Table 3: Characteristics of G1004

This sherd has a notch (handle?). This sherd fits the description of fine ware by Evans (1971, p.208).

Archaeological context This sherd was excavated from Santa Verna by the FRAG-SUS project (McLaughlin et al., 2020b), Trench D Northern extension, stratigraphic unit (63). (63) was AMS dated to 5300-5025 cal. BC (McLaughlin et al., 2020c, p.114), which would fit during the Skorba phase (Hunt et al., 2020, p.37). However, the presence of Żebbuġ pottery pieces in this layer and the underlying layer (113) suggests disturbance in later periods.

G1004 is therefore a residual sherd, sampled based on the diagnostic decoration.

G1006

Figure 4: (a) Interior and exterior of G1006 (b) Microphotograph: G1006 ground edge

Other identifiers and previous publications GD1-3F-113-1 (MaltaPot); SV113-2 (Malone et al., 2020, 326, description, drawing in Fig. 10.7:8)

Description

Sherd type	Base of handle
Typology	Evans Għar Dalam 4
Macroscopic Ware classification	Coarse ware, transitional to Skorba
Wall thickness	5.86 mm
Surface treatment	chevron pattern, incised on the handle
Surfaces Interior	10YR 5/2 grayish brown
Surfaces Exterior	7.5YR 3/1 very dark gray
Core colour	10YR 4/1 dark gray
Margin colour	10YR 4/1 dark gray

Table 4: Characteristics of G1006

Archaeological context This sherd was excavated from Santa Verna by the FRAG-SUS project (McLaughlin et al., 2020b), Trench D Northern extension, stratigraphic unit (113). This layer is beneath (63) from which G1004 was extracted. Context (113) contained material radio-carbon dated to 5325-5075 cal. BC (McLaughlin et al., 2020b, p.144), placing deposition during the Skorba phase (Hunt et al., 2020, p.37). Considering that Żebbuġ phase sherds were found, however, the context was later disturbed (McLaughlin et al., 2020b, p.144).

This sherd was sampled based on its diagnostic shape and decoration as the chevron pattern is typical of the Għar Dalam period fine ware (Malone et al., 2020, p.325).

G1011

Figure 5: (a) Exterior and interior of G1011 (b) Microphotograph: G1011 ground edge

Other identifiers and previous publications GD1-3F-7-3

Description

Sherd type	Body / lug
Typology	Evans Għar Dalam 4
Macroscopic Ware classification	Fine Ware
Wall thickness	4.49 mm
Surface treatment	Rough surface with surface inclusions, some impressions barely visible
Surfaces Interior	5Y 4/1 dark gray
Surfaces Exterior	2.5Y 2.5/1 black
Core colour	5Y 3/1 Very dark gray
Margin colour	5Y 3/1 Very dark gray

Table 5: Characteristics of G1011

Archaeological context This sherd was excavated from Santa Verna in 2015 by the FRAGSUS project (McLaughlin et al., 2020b), Trench B, context (7), away (North-East) from the temple structure (McLaughlin et al., 2020b, p.133). Context (7) is the top layer of this trench which had only three units with a concentration of Neolithic sherds but no *in-situ* features (McLaughlin et al., 2020b, p.135).

This sherd was sampled based on typology.

G1026

Figure 6: (a) Exterior and interior of G1026 (b) Microphotograph: G1026 ground edge

Other identifiers and previous publications GD1-4T-?-6 (MaltaPot); SKCB4 (NMA)

Description

Sherd type	Rim
Typology	Evans Għar Dalam 3 or 4
Macroscopic Ware classification	Fine ware
Wall thickness	5.26 mm
Surface treatment	Burnished surfaces, common in Għar Dalam phase sherds (Malone et al., 2020, p.325)
Surfaces Interior	10YR 4/1 dark gray
Surfaces Exterior	7.5YR 4/1 dark gray
Core colour	10YR 3/1 very dark gray

Table 6: Characteristics of G1026

Archaeological context This sherd was excavated from the site of Skorba by D. Trump (Trump, 1966; 2015), and extracted from the National Museum of Archaeology (NMA), Malta (Box 70). It was found in trench CB (layer 4), situated south-west of the Western temple excavated in the spring of 1962. According to Trump (1962b, p.15), this layer is a "Stony grey" layer with Grey Skorba pottery and Zebbuġ pottery intrusive.

This sherd was sampled based on typology and surface treatment.

G1028

Figure 7: (a) Interior and exterior of G1028 (b) Microphotograph: G1028 ground edge

Other identifiers and previous publications GD1-4T-?-3 (MaltaPot); SKJD2 (NMA)

Description

Sherd type	Body/shoulder with start of handle
Typology	Evans Għar Dalam 4
Macroscopic Ware classification	Fine
Wall thickness	4.58 mm
Surface treatment	Impressed pattern 'C' and horizontal line and burnished
Surfaces Interior	10YR 5/1 gray
Surfaces Exterior	10YR 2/1 black
Core colour	10YR 2/1 black

Table 7: Characteristics of G1028

Archaeological context This sherd was excavated from the site of Skorba by D. Trump (Trump, 1966; 2015), and extracted from the National Museum of Archaeology (NMA), Malta (Box 69). It was found in trench JD (layer 2), situated in the area of the Neolithic "village" (Trump, 2015, p.28) and opened in the autumn of 1962. Layer 2 is a "V. hard stone and clay" layer (Trump, 1962c, p.47) which yielded mixed Għar Dalam and Grey Skorba phase pottery (Trump, 1962c, 52r).

This sherd was sampled based on typology and decoration. The decoration, and its placement on the shoulder, have parallels in Malone et al. (2020, 328 figs 10.7: 16, 18).

G1030

Figure 8: (a) Exterior and interior of G1030 (b) Microphotograph: G1030 ground edge

Other identifiers and previous publications N/A

Description

Sherd type	Body sherd
Macroscopic Ware classification	Fine, with some white inclusions
Wall thickness	7.93
Surface treatment	Impressed or incised parallel lines. White paste.
Surfaces Interior	10YR 4/1 dark gray
Surfaces Exterior	10YR 6/2 light brownish gray
Margin colour	10YR 7/3 very pale brown and 10YR 4/1 dark gray

Table 8: Characteristics of G1030

Archaeological context This sherd was excavated from Santa Verna by the FRAG-SUS project (McLaughlin et al., 2020b), Trench D Northern extension, stratigraphic unit (63). This context was described in the entry G1004.

This sherd was selected based on the decoration.

G1037

Figure 9: (a) **Exterior and interior of G1037** (b) Microphotograph: G1037 ground edge

Other identifiers and previous publications GD1-4F-24-4 (MaltaPot)

Description

Sherd type	Body
Macroscopic Ware classification	Fine
Wall thickness	7.95 mm
Surface treatment	Burnishing on both surfaces
Surfaces Interior	10YR 2/1 black
Surfaces Exterior	10YR 7/4 very pale brown
Margin colour	7.5YR 5/6 strong brown and 10YR 6/1 gray

Table 9: Characteristics of G1037

Archaeological context This sherd was excavated from a sondage at the site of Skorba in 2015 by the FRAGSUS project (Brogan et al., 2020), stratigraphic unit (24). This layer is illustrated in section and matrix in Brogan et al. (2020, p.232) and contained mostly Skorba material although Għar Dalam phase sherds were found. A radiocarbon date gave 5280 to 4960 cal. BC (Brogan et al., 2020, p.234), which would date the deposition to the Skorba phase (Hunt et al., 2020, p.37). This layer seems to be *in situ* but dated to the Skorba phase.

This sherd was sampled based on ware and stratigraphy.

G1043

Figure 10: (a) Exterior and interior of G1043 (b) Microphotograph: G1043 ground edge

Other identifiers and previous publications GD1-4T?-?-2 (MaltaPot); SKMC4 (NMA)

Description

Sherd type	Lug/knob
Typology	known in ovoid vessels with narrow necks or open trunco-conical vessels
Macroscopic Ware classification	Fine
Wall thickness	13.74 mm
Surface treatment	Burnished on outer surface
Surfaces Interior	10YR 7/1 light gray
Surfaces Exterior	10YR 8/1 white
Core colour	10YR 5/1 gray

Table 10: Characteristics of G1043

Archaeological context This sherd was excavated from the site of Skorba by D. Trump (Trump, 1966; 2015), and extracted from the National Museum of Archaeology (NMA), Malta (Box 69). It was found in trench MC (layer 4), situated close to the South room of the Neolithic "village" (Trump, 2015, pp.31–32) and opened in the autumn of 1962. This layer is a Għar Dalam layer - "Hard clayey with stones" - overlaying a sterile layer (Trump, 1962d, pp.37–38). In section, it seems to be butting the wall of a Neolithic "room" (Trump, 1962d, p.38) and Trump mentions that the outer face of the wall for the Skorba phase "shrine" had earlier deposits butting it (Trump, 2015, p.33).

This sherd was sampled based on typology and stratigraphy.

G1048

Figure 11: (a) **Exterior and interior of G1048** (b) Microphotograph: G1048 ground edge

Other identifiers and previous publications GD1-4F-24-3 (MaltaPot)

Description

Sherd type	Body
Macroscopic Ware classification	Transitional Ware
Wall thickness	10.85 mm
Surface treatment	Burnished on both sides
Surfaces Interior	7.5YR 6/6 reddish yellow
Surfaces Exterior	7.5YR 7/6 reddish yellow
Core colour	7.5YR 5/1 gray

Table 11: Characteristics of G1048

Archaeological context This sherd was excavated from a sondage at the site of Skorba in 2015 by the FRAGSUS project (Brogan et al., 2020), stratigraphic unit (24). See the description in entry G1037.

This sherd was sampled based on ware description and stratigraphy.

G1049

Figure 12: (a) **Exterior and interior** of G1049 (b) Microphotograph: G1049 ground edge

Other identifiers and previous publications GD1-4F-24-2 (MaltaPot)

Description

Sherd type	Body
Macroscopic Ware classification	Transitional Ware
Wall thickness	9.82 mm
Surface treatment	Burnished surfaces
Surfaces Interior	7.5YR 6/4 light brown
Surfaces Exterior	7.5YR 7/6 reddish yellow
Core colour	7.5YR 6/3 light brown and 7.5YR 5/1 gray

Table 12: Characteristics of G1049

Archaeological context This sherd was excavated from a sondage at the site of Skorba in 2015 by the FRAGSUS project (Brogan et al., 2020), stratigraphic unit (24). See the description in entry G1037.

This sherd was selected based on ware descriptions and stratigraphy.

G2005

Figure 13: (a) Exterior and interior of G2005 (b) Microphotograph: G2005 ground edge

Other identifiers and previous publications GD2-3F-8-1 (MaltaPot)

Description

Sherd type	Body
Macroscopic Ware classification	Coarse Ware
Wall thickness	15.51 mm
Surface treatment	Chevron pattern on exterior surface and bur-nished interior surface
Surfaces Interior	7.5YR 6/4 light brown
Surfaces Exterior	10YR 7/4 very pale brown
Core colour	7.5YR 6/4 light brown

Table 13: Characteristics of G2005

Because of its crumbling and soft (nail scratch) texture and thick wall, this sherd was classified as coarse ware. However, the matrix is compact and the visible voids are not macro-voids and cracks.

Archaeological context This sherd was excavated from Santa Verna in 2015 by the FRAGSUS project (McLaughlin et al., 2020b), Trench B, context (8), away (North-East) from the temple structure (McLaughlin et al., 2020b, p.133). This context is similar to context (7) from which G1011 was sampled. Sherds from later periods were found in this layer (McLaughlin et al., 2020b, p.135), however, this context had a concentration of Għar Dalam sherds which was described as "the best representations of Għar Dalam pottery" of the layers at Santa Verna (McLaughlin et al., 2020b, 153, Fig. 4.42).

This sherd was sampled because of its diagnostic chevron pattern.

G2006

Figure 14: (a) Exterior and interior of G2006 (b) Microphotograph: G2006 ground edge

Other identifiers and previous publications N/A

Description

Sherd type	Body
Macroscopic Ware classification	Coarse Ware
Wall thickness	9.54 mm
Surface treatment	burnished interior surface and chevron pattern (incised?) on unburnished exterior surface
Surfaces Interior	10YR 5/4 yellowish brown
Surfaces Exterior	10YR 5/1 gray
Margin colour	10YR 6/4 light yellowish brown and 10YR 5/2 grayish brown

Table 14: Characteristics of G2006

Archaeological context This sherd was excavated from Santa Verna in 2015 by the FRAGSUS project (McLaughlin et al., 2020b), Trench E, context (89), in the vicinity of the temple structure (McLaughlin et al., 2020b, pp.137, 146). This context was described in entry G2004 in (Richard-Trémeau et al., 2023).

This sherd was sampled because of its diagnostic chevron pattern.

G2008

Figure 15: (a) Exterior and interior of G2008 (b) Microphotograph: G2008 ground edge

Other identifiers and previous publications GD2-3F-63-1 (MaltaPot)

Description

Sherd type	Handle
Typology	Found in different globular jar types (eg. Evans type 4)
Macroscopic Ware classification	Transitional
Wall thickness	13.83
Surface treatment	Burnished
Surfaces Interior	10YR 3/1 very dark gray
Surfaces Exterior	10YR 6/3 pale brown
Core colour	2.5YR 5/3 reddish brown
Margin colour	10YR 5/1 gray

Table 15: Characteristics of G2008

For handle descriptions, see Malone et al. (2020, p.325)

Archaeological context This sherd was excavated from Santa Verna by the FRAG-SUS project (McLaughlin et al., 2020b), Trench D Northern extension, stratigraphic unit (63). This context was described in the entry G1004.

This sherd was sampled based on typology.

G2015

Figure 16: (a) Exterior and interior of G2015 (b) Microphotograph: G2015 ground edge

Other identifiers and previous publications GD2-3F-89-2 (MaltaPot)

Description

Sherd type	Body with start of handle
Macroscopic Ware classification	comment similar to G2005
Wall thickness	10.94 mm
Surface treatment	burnished exterior surface, untreated interior surface
Surfaces Interior	7.5YR 6/4 light brown
Surfaces Exterior	7.5YR 6/4 light brown
Core colour	7.5YR 5/6 strong brown

Table 16: Characteristics of G2015

Archaeological context This sherd was excavated from Santa Verna by the FRAG-SUS project (McLaughlin et al., 2020b), Trench D Northern extension, stratigraphic unit (113). (113) underlies context (63) described for sherds G1004 and G2008, and also contains Ġħar Dalam, Skorba and Żebbuġ phases pottery. The material was dated between 5325 to 5075 cal. BC, similar dates to context (63), placing the deposition of both layers during the Skorba period (Hunt et al., 2020, p.37) but with later disturbance.

This sherd was sampled based on ware descriptions.

G2019

Figure 17: (a) Exterior and interior of G2019 (b) Microphotograph: G2019 ground edge

Other identifiers and previous publications GD1-3F-90-2 (MaltaPot); SV90-2 (Malone et al., 2020, 350, fig 10.16:13)

Description

Sherd type	Body
Macroscopic Ware classification	Coarse
Wall thickness	13.33 mm
Surface treatment	chevron pattern
Surfaces Interior	7.5YR 5/3 brown
Surfaces Exterior	7.5YR 6/3 light brown
Core colour	7.5YR 5/2 brown
Margin colour	7.5YR 5/6 strong brown

Table 17: Characteristics of G2019

Archaeological context This sherd was excavated from Santa Verna by the FRAG-SUS project (McLaughlin et al., 2020b, 147 for section Fig. 4.33), Trench E stratigraphic unit (90). This layer mainly contained Għar Dalam and Skorba sherds with intrusive Żebbuġ sherds (McLaughlin et al., 2020b, p.146). Four radiocarbon dates suggest a deposition during the early Skorba period.

This sherd was first classified as Għar Dalam at the time of sampling because of the incised decorations and the similarities to the known coarse fabric, and because the context was predominantly Skorba and Għar Dalam. However, it was then published as from the Żebbuġ phase in Malone et al. (2020, 350, Fig. SV90-2) by comparison to sherds from contexts dated to the Żebbuġ period from Taċ-Ċawla. Indeed, although the geometric patterns are often associated with the Għar Dalam period, they are known in the Żebbuġ phase. Further characterisation is needed.

5 Skorba phase pottery

Fourteen sherds were catalogued for the Skorba phase, mainly excavated from the archaeological site of Skorba (Malta) either from the recent excavations or from the material excavated by D. Trump stored at the NMA. Four samples were sourced from Santa Verna (Gozo), Taċ-Ċawla (Gozo) and Kordin III (Malta). These sites are summarised in the open-access chapters from the FRAGSUS project Brogan et al. (2020), Malone et al. (2020c), and McLaughlin et al. (2020a,b).

The entry for sample S6012 is available in Richard-Trémeau et al. (2023).

S1003

Figure 18: (a) Exterior and interior of S1003 (b) Microphotograph: S1003 ground edge

Other identifiers and previous publications GS1-4T-?-13 (MaltaPot); SKJD1 (NMA); 33583 (NMA)

Description

Sherd type	Rim
Typology	Evans Gsk 4
Macroscopic Ware classification	Fine ware
Wall thickness	8.89 mm
Surface treatment	Burnshished surfaces, lighter outer surface (slipped?)
Surfaces Interior	2.5Y 5/1 gray
Surfaces Exterior	10YR 7/3 very pale brown and 2.5Y 5/1 gray
Core colour	GLE Y 1 5/N

Table 18: Characteristics of S1003

Archaeological context This sherd was sourced from the collection of the NMA from the old excavations (Box 71) at the site of Skorba by David Trump (Trump, 1966). It was found in trench JD opened in the autumn of 1962, layer 1. Trench JD was excavated in the Eastern part of the site, close to the Red Skorba "shrine" (Trump, 2015, p.31). Trench JD was described in entry G1028; layer one is the topsoil mixed by ploughing (Trump, 1962c, p.47).

This sherd was sampled based on location and ware description.

NMA description, by S. Pirani "1 rim sherd with an handle abutment on the external surface and a part of the handle is preserved: probably a Skorba lug type. The surfaces appear light gray/pink and gray smoothed."; Grey Skorba; thickness: 0.8 cm.

S1010

Figure 19: (a) Exterior and interior of S1010 (b) Microphotograph: S1010 ground edge

Other identifiers and previous publications GS1-4T-?-12 (MaltaPot); SKB6 (NMA); 33550 (NMA)

Description

Sherd type	Strap handle
Typology	Possible ladle?
Macroscopic Ware classification	Fine Ware
Wall thickness	13.43
Surface treatment	Surface inclusions visible
Surfaces Interior	7.5YR 5/2 brown
Surfaces Exterior	7.5YR 5/2 brown and 5YR 6/3 light reddish brown
Core colour	7.5YR 4/2 brown
Margin colour	5YR 6/4 light reddish brown and 5YR 4/1 dark gray

Table 19: Characteristics of S1010

Archaeological context This sherd was sourced from the collection of the NMA from the old excavations (Box 71) at the site of Skorba by David Trump (Trump, 1966). It was found in Trench B, opened in the spring of 1961, layer 6. This layer contained mostly Skorba phase pottery (Trump, 1961, p.17) and seemed to have been burrowed (Trump, 1961, section 18). For Trump, this is a Skorba occupation level with a few intrusive sherds brought by roots (Trump, 1961, 29 1.-29 r.).

This sherd was sampled because of its typology and context.

NMA description, by S. Pirani "1 thick handle sherd (maybe coarse ware) with light brown rubbed surfaces."; Grey Skorba; max thickness: 1.6 cm.

S1021

Figure 20: (a) Exterior and interior of S1021 (b) Microphotograph: S1021 ground edge

Other identifiers and previous publications GS1-3F-63-1

Description

Sherd type	Body
Macroscopic Ware classification	Fine ware
Wall thickness	7.98 mm
Surface treatment	evenly burnished surfaces
Surfaces Interior	5Y 5/1 gray
Surfaces Exterior	GLEY 1 4/1 dark greenish gray and 5Y 5/1 gray
Core colour	GLEY 1 5/1 greenish gray

Table 20: Characteristics of S1021

Archaeological context This sherd was excavated from Santa Verna by the FRAG-SUS project (McLaughlin et al., 2020b), Trench D Northern extension, stratigraphic unit (63). This context was described in the entry G1004.

This sherd was sampled based on its context and surface treatment.

S2007

Figure 21: (a) Exterior and interior of S2007 (b) Microphotograph: S2007 ground edge

Other identifiers and previous publications GS2-4F-23-2 (MaltaPot)

Description

Sherd type	Rim
Typology	Sagona GSk 11
Macroscopic Ware classification	Fine ware
Wall thickness	10.21 mm
Surface treatment	Burnished surfaces
Surfaces Interior	10YR 7/2 light gray
Surfaces Exterior	10YR 7/2 light gray and 10YR 3/1 very dark gray
Core colour	10YR 4/1 dark gray
Margin colour	10YR 5/3 brown and 10YR 4/2 dark grayish brown

Table 21: Characteristics of S2007

Archaeological context This sherd was excavated from a sondage at the site of Skorba in 2015 by the FRAGSUS project (Brogan et al., 2020), stratigraphic unit (23). This context was described in the entry G1002.

This sherd was sampled based on ware descriptions for the Skorba phase pottery and typology.

S3002

Figure 22: (a) Exterior and interior of S3002 (b) Microphotograph: S3002 ground edge

Other identifiers and previous publications 33429 (NMA); SKZA4 (NMA)

Description

Sherd type	Rim
Typology	Evans RSk 6
Macroscopic Ware classification	Fine ware
Wall thickness	5.2 mm
Surface treatment	Red slip on both surfaces
Surfaces Interior	2.5YR 5/8 red
Surfaces Exterior	2.5YR 5/8 red
Core colour	5YR 6/1 gray
Margin colour	5YR 7/6 reddish yellow

Table 22: Characteristics of S3002

Archaeological context This sherd was sourced from the collection of the NMA from the old excavations (Box 74) at the site of Skorba by David Trump (Trump, 1966). It was found in trench ZA (layer 4), situated west of the Western temple, and opened in the autumn of 1961. This layer was dated to the Żebbuġ period (Trump, 1962d, page after p.58), however with many residual Grey Skorba and Red Skorba sherds (Trump, 1962a, 12 l.).

This sherd was sampled because of its typology and surface treatment.

NMA description, by S. Pirani Rim; Red Skorba, red slip. Max thickness: 0.5 cm.

S3004

Figure 23: (a) Exterior and interior of S3004 (b) Microphotograph: S3004 ground edge

Other identifiers and previous publications SKUC12 (NMA)

Description

Sherd type	Body
Macroscopic Ware classification	Fine ware
Wall thickness	4.67 mm
Surface treatment	Red slip
Surfaces Interior	5YR 6/6 light red
Surfaces Exterior	2.5YR 5/6 red
Core colour	5YR 5/1 reddish gray
Margin colour	5YR 6/6 reddish yellow

Table 23: Characteristics of S3004

Archaeological context This sherd was sourced from the collection of the NMA (Box 74) from the old excavations at the site of Skorba by David Trump (Trump, 1966). It was found in trench UC (layer 12), situated west of the Western temple, and opened in the autumn of 1962. It was extracted as a special find for the MaltaPot project. The layer is a Skorba phase layer, below a Żebbuġ layer which is itself sealed by a floor level (Trump, 1962c, p.43). Most of the pottery found was Skorba phase with only a few intrusive sherds (Trump, 1962c, 50r).

This sherd was sampled because of its surface treatment and context.

S3005

Figure 24: (a) Exterior and interior of S3005 (b) Microphotograph: S3005 ground edge

Other identifiers and previous publications RS1-4T-?-5 (MaltaPot); SKKE2 (NMA); 33386 (NMA)

Description

Sherd type	Rim
Typology	Inverted jar, see examples in Malone et al. (2020, 336, Fig. 10.9:12-18)
Macroscopic Ware classification	Fine ware
Wall thickness	7.68 mm
Surface treatment	Slipped? (red)
Surfaces Interior	7.5YR 7/4 pink
Surfaces Exterior	5YR 5/8 yellowish red and 2.5Y 6/1 gray
Margin colour	5YR 7/4 pink and 10YR 8/2 very pale brown

Table 24: Characteristics of S3005

Archaeological context This sherd was sourced from the collection of the NMA from the old excavations (Box 74) at the site of Skorba by David Trump (Trump, 1966). It was found in trench KE (layer 2), situated in the eastern part of the site in the area of the Early Neolithic "village" or Red Skorba "shrine" (Trump, 2015, p.31), and opened in the spring of 1963. This "Old Brown" layer (Trump, 1963, p.12) mostly contained Red Skorba pottery with a few Grey Skorba and Għar Dalam phase sherds (Trump, 1963, 25 l.).

This sherd was sampled because of its surface treatment and context.

NMA description, by S. Pirani "1 rim sherd with light brown and maybe red slipped surfaces."; Red Skorba; Max thickness: 0.8 mm.

S3008

Figure 25: (a) Exterior and interior of S3008 (b) Microphotograph: S3008 ground edge

Other identifiers and previous publications RS1-4T-?-1; SKGA8 (NMA); 33451 (NMA)

Description

Sherd type	Pedestal base?
Typology	Evans GSk 2
Macroscopic Ware classification	Fine Ware
Wall thickness	12.97 mm
Surface treatment	Red slip outer surface and burnish
Surfaces Interior	7.5YR 5/1 gray
Surfaces Exterior	2.5YR 5/6 red
Core colour	GLE Y 1 4/N dark gray

Table 25: Characteristics of

Archaeological context This sherd was sourced from the collection of the NMA from the old excavations (Box 74) at the site of Skorba by David Trump (Trump, 1966). It was found in trench GA (layer 8), in the north-west of the Western temple, and opened in the autumn of 1961. This "orange stony to S, clayey to N" (Trump, 1962d, p.62) was interpreted as a Red Skorba layer and was rich in Red Skorba pottery, among other finds such as chert (Trump, 1962a, 11 r.).

This sherd was sampled based on typology, context and surface decoration.

NMA description, by S. Pirani "1 inverted pedestal sherd with red external slip and light brown rubbed and very porous inner surface."; Red Skorba; Max thickness: 1.3 cm.

S3010

Figure 26: (a) Exterior and interior of S3010 (b) Microphotograph: S3010 ground edge

Other identifiers and previous publications RS1-4T-?-10 (MaltaPot); SKLD5 (NMA); 33485 (NMA)

Description

Sherd type	Rim
Typology	pointy rim such as Evans Rsk 7
Macroscopic Ware classification	Fine Ware
Wall thickness	6.21 mm
Surface treatment	Burnished, slipped?
Surfaces Interior	5YR 4/6 yellowish red and 5YR 5/6 yellowish red
Surfaces Exterior	7.5YR 4/6 strong brown and 5YR 5/6 yellowish red
Core colour	5YR 6/4 light reddish brown

Table 26: Characteristics of S3010

Archaeological context This sherd was sourced from the collection of the NMA from the old excavations (Box 74) at the site of Skorba by David Trump (Trump, 1966). It was found in trench LD (layer 5), situated in the "Neolithic village" or "Shrine"; in the "South room" (Trump, 2015, p.32), and opened in the autumn of 1962. This trench underneath the top soil had several Red-Skorba layers, and layer 5 ("Stiff Grey Clay") is the first occupation in the trench (Trump, 1962c, p.49). All the pottery was Red Skorba except for two intrusive sherds (Trump, 1962c, p.53).

This sherd was sampled based on typology, context and surface treatment.

NMA description, by S. Pirani "1 rim sherd with reddish gray polished surfaces."; Red Skorba; Max thickness: 0.4 cm.

S6001

Figure 27: (a) Exterior and interior of S6001 (b) Microphotograph: S6001 ground edge

Other identifiers and previous publications SK2-4F-16-1 (MaltaPot)

Description

Sherd type	Body sherd
Macroscopic Ware classification	Coarse ware
Wall thickness	13.25
Surface treatment	N/A
Surfaces Interior	5YR 2.5/1 black and 7.5YR 4/3 brown
Surfaces Exterior	5YR 6/6 reddish yellow
Core colour	5YR 5/6 yellowish red
Margin colour	7.5YR 6/4 light brown and 7.5YR 5/3 brown

Table 27: Characteristics of S6001

Archaeological context This sherd was excavated from a sondage at the Eastern corner at the site of Skorba in 2015 by the FRAGSUS project (Brogan et al., 2020, 234 for matrix and section), context (16). This context overlays a pre-temple context (19) including Żebbuġ phase pottery. Context (16) contained pottery from diverse phases and yielded a radiocarbon date from the Skorba period (Brogan et al., 2020, p.235). Stratigraphically, however, the Neolithic sherds in this unit are likely redeposited.

This sherd was sampled based on ware descriptions.

S6003

Figure 28: (a) Exterior and interior of S6003 (b) Microphotograph: S6003 ground edge

Other identifiers and previous publications**Description**

Sherd type	Body/knob
Typology	Similar knobs illustrated in Malone et al. (2020, 338, Fig. 10.11:10)
Macroscopic Ware classification	Coarse Ware
Wall thickness	12.76 mm
Surface treatment	Burnished surfaces
Surfaces Interior	7.5YR 4/1 dark gray
Surfaces Exterior	5YR 5/6 yellowish red
Core colour	2.5YR 3/1 very dark gray
Margin colour	5YR 5/6 yellowish red and 7.5YR 4/1 dark gray

Table 28: Characteristics of S6003

Archaeological context This sherd was excavated from a sondage at the Eastern corner at the site of Skorba in 2015 by the FRAGSUS project (Brogan et al., 2020, 234 for matrix and section), context (11). This context yielded pottery from the Early Neolithic to the Roman period.

This sherd was sampled based on ware descriptions.

S6006

Figure 29: (a) Exterior and interior of S6006 (b) Microphotograph: S6006 ground edge

Other identifiers and previous publications N/A

Description

Sherd type	Body
Macroscopic Ware classification	Coarse Ware
Wall thickness	9.6 mm
Surface treatment	surface inclusions visible and wiping marks
Surfaces Interior	GLEY 1 2.5/N black
Surfaces Exterior	5YR 6/4 light reddish brown
Core colour	5YR 6/4 light reddish brown
Margin colour	GLEY 1 2.5/N black

Table 29: Characteristics of S6006

Archaeological context This sherd was excavated from the site of Taċ-Ċawla, during the FRAGSUS excavations (Malone et al., 2020c), layer (193-194). These layers, equated in Malone et al. (2020c, p.74), were described as floor levels that were then disturbed in later periods and cut by later features (Malone et al., 2020c, p.95). The dating of the layer is uncertain as Malone et al. (2020c, p.56) mentions a Bronze Age date.

This sherd was sampled based on ware descriptions.

S6015

Figure 30: (a) Exterior and interior of S6015 (b) Microphotograph: S6015 ground edge

Other identifiers and previous publications N/A

Description

Sherd type	Body
Macroscopic Ware classification	Coarse Ware
Wall thickness	19.12 mm
Surfaces Interior	7.5YR 4/1 dark gray
Surfaces Exterior	7.5YR 6/4 light brown
Core colour	7.5YR 5/2 brown
Margin colour	7.5YR 6/4 light brown and 7.5YR 4/1 dark gray

Table 30: Characteristics of S6015

Archaeological context This sherd was excavated from the site of Kordin III during the FRAGSUS excavations (McLaughlin et al., 2020a), layer (147). This layer mainly yielded Mgarr phase pottery and a radiocarbon date of 3630-3375 BC (McLaughlin et al., 2020a, 216, see plan Fig. 6.38).

This sherd was sampled based on ware descriptions.

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